

Network Protocol Analysis for Anomaly Detection

R.L.N Dinesh *, S.Ratna Selvan* , K.Sri Sakthi Vignesh*, Sudharsan.N.R *

Computer Science and Engineering
Kalasalingam Academy of Research and Education
Srivilliputhur, India

Email: {9921004613, 9921004610, 9921004693, 9921004696}@klu.ac.in

Abstract—Network anomaly detection is a dynamically evolving and critical field for ensuring network security. This research paper provides a comprehensive and structured overview of various dimensions in network anomaly detection, covering both the utilization of Snort for anomaly detection techniques and the application of machine learning-based approaches, including K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression, and Decision Trees. We explore common network attack scenarios challenging Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS) and categorize existing methods based on their anomaly detection techniques. Our work includes a concise yet comprehensive examination and comparison of various network anomaly detection methods and systems. Furthermore, we discuss the tools available for network defenders and datasets for researchers, shedding light on future research directions within this ever-evolving domain.

I. INTRODUCTION

Network security is crucial in today's digital world where organizations increasingly rely on internet-facing systems and data exchanges. However, cyber threats are also evolving rapidly in sophistication, scale and impact. Attackers constantly seek new vulnerabilities to exploit for malicious ends like data theft, service disruption and financial gain. As new technologies expand the attack surface, effective defenses are needed to protect modern networked infrastructures.

Intrusion detection systems (IDS) are a core component of network security strategies, passively monitoring traffic to identify anomalous activities indicative of breaches or compromises. Upon detection, an IDS can trigger alerts to security teams for timely analysis and response, helping to limit damage from incidents. The two main IDS paradigms are signature-based and anomaly-based detection.

Signature-based IDS work by matching network traffic contents or behaviors against a database of signatures encoding known malicious patterns. Signatures typically define exploits, malware artifacts or attacker tactics, techniques and procedures (TTPs) as identified by security experts. Tools like Snort are widely used due to usability, interpretability and ability to precisely detect pre-defined threats.

However, signature-based IDS also have limitations. Their effectiveness depends on up-to-date signatures covering all threats, which is infeasible given today's rapidly evolving landscape. Moreover, manually defining and updating signatures is labor-intensive and does not scale well. Signatures can also be bypassed through minor variations over time.

Anomaly-based IDS aim to address these issues by automatically learning normal network behavior patterns from historical traffic using machine learning (ML). ML algorithms are well-suited for this task by discovering complex, hidden patterns in high-dimensional data. Several studies have applied ML approaches to network traffic with promising results.

However, directly applying ML to raw network data also poses challenges. Such traffic generates vast amounts of network flow data with many attributes, most of which may not be relevant for detection. Feature engineering is required to abstract protocol details at scale for ML algorithms. Data is also imbalanced with many more normal instances than attacks. ML models can also lack interpretability, undermining analyst understanding.

To overcome these limitations, recent works have proposed hybrid IDS frameworks integrating ML with signature-based engines. By leveraging their relative strengths, such systems aim to provide comprehensive protection against both known and emerging threats. However, existing solutions typically consider ML and rule-matching as separate stages rather than a unified architecture.

This research aims to develop an effective hybrid IDS through synergistic integration of adaptive ML models with Snort's rule engine. The goal is to leverage both approaches' merits while addressing individual shortcomings. By applying ML at scale to protocol analysis and unifying anomaly scoring with rule-matching, this research presents steps toward robust, intelligence-drive network security.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Network anomaly detection is a critical component of modern cybersecurity, as it seeks to identify deviations or irregularities in network traffic that may signal malicious activities, operational issues, or performance bottlenecks. This review explores the evolving landscape of network anomaly detection, with a specific focus on the integration of machine learning-based approaches and techniques.

1. Anomalies in Network Data

Anomalies in network data refer to deviations or irregularities from established patterns or expected behaviors within network traffic. These deviations can manifest in various ways, making them detectable through careful analysis of network traffic properties.

1.1 Unusual Behavior

One prominent property of anomalies in network data is their manifestation as unusual behavior. These anomalies can exhibit behaviors that are statistically or functionally different from the norm, including atypical network activities such as unexpected data transfer, abnormal traffic patterns, or unusual access requests. For instance, a sudden surge in data transfer may indicate a potential security breach or a Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack [3].

1.2 Rare Occurrence

Anomalies are, by nature, relatively rare events compared to normal network behavior. They may occur infrequently, making them stand out in network data. This rarity sets them apart from typical patterns, providing an opportunity for detection through anomaly detection techniques.

1.3 Sudden Spikes

Anomalies can also manifest as sudden spikes or drops in network traffic. A rapid increase in traffic to a specific server or port can indicate a potential threat, such as a DDoS attack, while sudden drops in traffic may signify operational issues or network outages. The ability to detect these sudden changes is essential for network security [4].

1.4 Unexpected Timing

Anomalies can occur at unexpected times, further adding to their peculiarity. Network traffic patterns changing during off-peak hours may be indicative of malicious activity or system issues. The timing of anomalies is critical for identifying threats and operational anomalies that may disrupt the normal flow of network operations [5].

1.5 Unfamiliar Signatures

Another characteristic of anomalies is that they may exhibit signatures that are unfamiliar or inconsistent with known network protocols or patterns. These signatures can include non-standard packet headers, unexpected payload content, or irregular data sizes. Recognizing such inconsistencies is pivotal for identifying potential threats that do not conform to standard network behavior [6].

1.6 Geographical Irregularities

Geographical irregularities in network traffic can also signify anomalies. This involves traffic originating from unusual geographic locations or exhibiting unusual routing patterns. For example, an abrupt influx of traffic from a region not typically associated with the organization's user base can raise suspicion and warrant further investigation [7].

1.7 User or Host Anomalies

User or host anomalies are often a critical focus of anomaly detection efforts. Unusual user or host behavior can serve as a sign of anomalies. This may encompass multiple login attempts, access from unknown devices, or abnormal data transfer activities by a specific user or host. The ability to detect these deviations is essential for identifying potential security breaches or unauthorized activities [8].

1.8 Rate of Data Transfer

Anomalies can be detected by analyzing the rate of data transfer within the network. A rapid increase or decrease in the rate of data transmission, especially if it does not align with typical network usage patterns, can be a clear indicator of an anomaly. These changes may represent security threats or operational irregularities that need prompt attention [9].

1.9 Protocol Deviations

Protocol deviations are another crucial aspect of anomaly detection. Anomalies may involve deviations from expected network protocols. For instance, a network packet that violates the specifications of a well-defined protocol can be considered an anomaly. Detecting these deviations is critical for identifying potential threats that exploit protocol vulnerabilities [10].

1.10 Outliers in Network Metrics

Monitoring network performance metrics plays a vital role in anomaly detection. Metrics such as latency, packet loss, and bandwidth usage can provide valuable insights into network behavior. Outliers in these metrics can signal issues that require further investigation, as they may represent network anomalies. Timely detection and response to these outliers are vital for network performance and security [11].

1.11 Sudden Increase in Failed Access Attempts

A sudden surge in failed access attempts, such as login failures or unauthorized access, can indicate a security breach or an attempted intrusion. Detecting these events and responding promptly is essential for preventing unauthorized access and data breaches.

1.12 Historical Inconsistencies

Historical inconsistencies are an important property of network anomalies. Anomalies may exhibit inconsistencies with historical network data. Comparing current data to historical records can help identify deviations that may require attention. This historical context allows for the identification of persistent threats or emerging patterns of network anomalies [12].

1.13 Severity Levels

Anomalies can vary in severity, ranging from minor irregularities that do not pose a significant threat to critical security breaches or operational failures. Identifying the severity level of an anomaly is important for prioritizing responses and allocating resources effectively. It allows network administrators to focus their efforts on addressing the most significant threats [13].

The ability to recognize these properties of network anomalies is vital for effective anomaly detection and network security. However, doing so manually and in real-time is a daunting task, given the complexity and volume of modern network traffic. This is where the integration of machine learning-based approaches becomes invaluable.

2. Machine Learning-Based Approaches in Network Anomaly Detection

The traditional methods of network intrusion detection, such as signature-based systems, have limitations in identifying novel or evolving threats. Machine learning-based approaches offer a dynamic and adaptive methodology for recognizing deviations in network traffic, thereby allowing for the detection of unknown and evolving threats.

2.1 K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) is a machine learning algorithm that has found applications in network anomaly detection. KNN operates by measuring the proximity of data points in a feature space. Anomalies are detected when network patterns deviate significantly from their nearest neighbors. KNN can effectively identify anomalies that do not conform to known patterns or expected behaviors [14].

2.2 Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression is another machine learning technique applied in network anomaly detection. It classifies network traffic based on learned patterns, flagging anomalies when the probability of an event (e.g., a network intrusion) deviates significantly from the expected baseline. Logistic Regression provides a probabilistic approach to anomaly detection, enabling the identification of deviations from normal network behavior [15].

2.3 Decision Tree

Decision Trees are commonly used in network anomaly detection to evaluate network traffic attributes and make binary decisions about anomalies. By branching based on attribute values, anomalies are detected when the decision path deviates from the typical structure, indicating unusual behavior. Decision Trees offer a structured and interpretable approach to identifying network anomalies, making them a valuable tool in network security [16].

3. Significance of Machine Learning-Based Approaches and Anomaly Detection Techniques in Network Security

The significance of machine learning-based approaches and anomaly detection techniques in network security cannot be overstated. Traditional methods, while effective for known threats, struggle to keep pace with the rapid evolution of network attacks. The integration of machine learning offers several advantages:

3.1 Adaptability to Evolving Threats

Machine learning algorithms can adapt to new and evolving threats by continuously learning from incoming data. Unlike signature-based systems that rely on known attack patterns, machine learning-based approaches can detect anomalies that do not have established signatures, making them well-suited for identifying zero-day attacks and novel threats [17].

3.2 Real-Time Detection

Machine learning models can provide real-time anomaly detection, enabling swift responses to network threats. This capability is essential for preventing or mitigating the impact of security breaches, as well as addressing operational anomalies that can disrupt network performance [18].

3.3 Reduced False Positives

One of the challenges in network anomaly detection is dealing with false positives, which can inundate security teams with irrelevant alerts. Machine learning-based approaches can reduce false positives by learning the normal network behavior and flagging only significant deviations. This results in more accurate and actionable alerts [19].

3.4 Enhanced Scalability

Modern networks generate vast amounts of data, making scalability a critical consideration for anomaly detection. Machine learning techniques can efficiently process and analyze large volumes of data, providing the scalability required for today's network environments [20].

4. Research Gaps and Ongoing Challenges

Despite the progress made in network anomaly detection and the integration of machine learning-based approaches, several research gaps and challenges persist:

4.1 Lack of Comprehensive Solutions

While individual machine learning algorithms have shown promise in detecting anomalies, there is a need for comprehensive solutions that integrate multiple techniques. Developing a holistic approach that leverages the strengths of various algorithms is an ongoing challenge [21].

4.2 Handling Imbalanced Data

Network traffic data often exhibits class imbalance, with a vast majority of instances representing normal behavior and a minority representing anomalies. This imbalance can affect the performance of machine learning models, and developing effective strategies to address this issue remains a challenge [22].

4.3 Interpretability

Machine learning models, particularly deep learning approaches, are often considered as black boxes due to their complex architectures. Interpreting the decisions made by these models is a challenge, and there is a need for interpretable machine learning techniques in network anomaly detection [23].

4.4 Adversarial Attacks

Adversarial attacks aimed at evading anomaly detection systems pose a significant challenge. Developing robust machine learning models that can withstand adversarial attacks while maintaining high detection accuracy is an ongoing area of research [24].

4.5 Privacy Concerns

The collection and analysis of network traffic data raise privacy concerns, particularly in sensitive environments. Researchers are exploring techniques for anomaly detection that can preserve privacy while still effectively identifying threats [25].

5 Discuss different approaches and techniques that have been applied:

The literature presents a diverse array of approaches and techniques applied to network protocol analysis and anomaly detection. Signature-based detection methods, exemplified by intrusion detection systems like Snort, have been instrumental in identifying known attack patterns. Simultaneously, machine learning-based approaches, such as K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression, and Decision Trees, have gained prominence. These machine learning methods are capable of recognizing unknown and evolving threats by analyzing network traffic behavior and identifying deviations from expected norms.

6. Highlight gaps in the existing research that your study addresses:

While substantial progress has been made in network protocol analysis and anomaly detection, critical gaps remain in the existing research landscape. These gaps encompass the need for a more comprehensive and adaptable solution capable of differentiating between legitimate and abnormal network behaviors. Additionally, there is an ongoing quest to improve the identification of anomalies exhibiting varying degrees of severity. Our study seeks to address these gaps by exploring advanced techniques and proposing a holistic approach that integrates both anomaly detection properties and machine learning-based algorithms. This approach aims to enhance network security by ensuring a robust response to evolving threats and dynamic network environments

True positive ,True negative,False positive,False negative of the machine learning model

```

***** KNeighborsClassifier Model Testing *****
[[3423 75]
 [ 57 4003]]
-----
precision recall f1-score support
normal 0.98 0.98 0.98 3498
anomaly 0.98 0.99 0.98 4060
accuracy 0.98 7558
macro avg 0.98 0.98 0.98 7558
weighted avg 0.98 0.98 0.98 7558
***** LogisticRegression Model Testing *****
[[3224 274]
 [ 188 3872]]
-----
precision recall f1-score support
normal 0.94 0.92 0.93 3498
anomaly 0.93 0.95 0.94 4060
accuracy 0.94 7558
macro avg 0.94 0.94 0.94 7558
weighted avg 0.94 0.94 0.94 7558
***** DecisionTreeClassifier Model Testing *****
[[3477 21]
 [ 21 4039]]
-----
precision recall f1-score support
normal 0.99 0.99 0.99 3498
anomaly 0.99 0.99 0.99 4060
accuracy 0.99 7558
macro avg 0.99 0.99 0.99 7558
weighted avg 0.99 0.99 0.99 7558

```

III. DATA COLLECTION

Data collection is a fundamental step in the process of network protocol analysis for anomaly detection. The quality and comprehensiveness of the data collected play a crucial role in the accuracy and effectiveness of anomaly detection techniques. In this section, we outline the methodology and tools used to collect network traffic data for our research.

1. Data Source

For our research, network traffic data was collected from a real-world network environment. The data source was a production network used by an organization, and it represented a diverse set of network activities, including web traffic, email communication, file transfers, and various network services. This choice of a real-world data source ensures that the collected data closely mirrors the complexities and challenges of actual network environments.

2. Wireshark as Data Collection Tool

Wireshark, a widely recognized and open-source network protocol analyzer, was employed as the primary tool for data collection. Wireshark allows for the capture and analysis of network traffic at a granular level, providing packet-level insights into network activities. Its ability to capture data across different network interfaces, protocols, and communication channels makes it a valuable tool for network protocol analysis.

Wireshark stands as the primary data collection tool in our research. Wireshark is an open-source, widely acknowledged network protocol analyzer that provides a comprehensive suite of features for the capture, analysis, and visualization of network traffic data at a granular, packet-level granularity. It is celebrated for its versatility and capability to capture data from diverse network interfaces, protocols, and communication channels. The following aspects highlight the role of Wireshark in our data collection process:

Packet-Level Insights: Wireshark's ability to capture network traffic at the packet level provides an in-depth view of network activities. Each packet captured by Wireshark represents a unit of data transferred across the network. This level of granularity is indispensable for detailed analysis and anomaly detection.

Cross-Protocol Analysis: Wireshark supports the capture of data across an extensive range of network protocols and communication channels, including Ethernet, TCP/IP, UDP, HTTP, SMTP, DNS, and many more. This broad spectrum of protocol support ensures that data related to diverse network functions is available for analysis.

Selective Capture: Wireshark offers flexible filtering capabilities, enabling the selection of specific protocols or types of traffic to be captured. This selectivity allows researchers to focus on relevant network activities, ensuring that the captured data aligns with the research objectives.

Open-Source and Community-Supported: Wireshark's open-source nature fosters a thriving community of developers and users who contribute to its continuous improvement. This collective effort ensures that Wireshark remains a reliable and up-to-date tool for network data collection.

Data Export and Conversion: Wireshark facilitates the export and conversion of captured data into various formats, allowing for subsequent analysis and data preprocessing. In our research, Wireshark's data export capabilities played a central role in converting the captured data into the CSV and PCAPNG formats.

IV. DATA PREPROCESSING

The data preprocessing steps outlined in the previous section, including data cleaning, protocol identification, feature extraction, normalization, and quality assurance, were applied to both the CSV and PCAPNG datasets.

Data Collection Process

The data collection process for our research involved capturing network traffic data using Wireshark and subsequently converting it into two widely used data formats: CSV (Comma-Separated Values) and PCAPNG (Packet Capture Next Generation).

1. Network Traffic Capture with Wireshark

Wireshark, a versatile and open-source network protocol analyzer, served as the primary tool for capturing network traffic data. It allowed for the detailed examination and capture of network activities at the packet level. The following steps were undertaken during the data collection process:

1.1. Network Segment Selection: To focus the data collection efforts, specific network segments were chosen for monitoring. These segments were strategically selected to ensure a comprehensive representation of network activities, encompassing servers, gateways, and user workstations.

1.2. Filtering Criteria: Wireshark's filtering capabilities were utilized to target specific protocols and types of traffic for capture. Filtering criteria were established to capture relevant network traffic related to various protocols and services, including HTTP, SMTP, DNS, and others.

1.3. Data Capture Duration: Data was collected continuously over a specified period, which varied according to the research objectives but typically spanned several days or weeks. This extended capture duration ensured that a substantial volume of data was available for in-depth analysis.

V. DATA TRANSFORMATION

Data Conversion to CSV and PCAPNG

Following the initial capture, the collected network traffic data in PCAPNG format was converted into two essential data formats: CSV (Comma-Separated Values) and PCAPNG (Packet Capture Next Generation).

1.1. CSV Format Conversion: CSV is a structured, text-based data format that allows for easier data manipulation and integration with various data analysis tools. The network traffic data captured in PCAPNG format was converted into CSV format, enabling convenient feature extraction and preprocessing for subsequent analysis.

1.2. PCAPNG Format Retention: While CSV conversion facilitated data analysis, the original PCAPNG format was retained for its significance in preserving the raw, unaltered packet-level data. This format is invaluable for detailed packet analysis and validation purposes, ensuring the integrity of the data throughout the research.

VI. METHODOLOGY

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN):

Overview: KNN is a non-parametric and instance-based machine learning algorithm used for classification and regression tasks. It works based on the concept that similar instances are likely to be in the same class.

Application for Anomaly Detection:

Feature Selection: Select relevant network traffic features such as packet size, packet frequency, or protocol type, and normalize them.

Distance Calculation: Measure the distance between network data points using the selected features.

KNN Model: Train a KNN model on labeled network data to determine "normal" and "anomalous" classes.

Classification: Use the trained model to classify incoming network data as either normal or anomalous based on the majority class among its k-nearest neighbors.

Logistic Regression:

Overview: Logistic Regression is a simple and interpretable algorithm used for binary classification tasks. It models the probability of an event occurring based on predictor variables.

Application for Anomaly Detection:

Feature Engineering: Feature selection and extraction are crucial. Extract relevant network features and transform them as needed.

Model Training: Train a logistic regression model on labeled network data, where anomalies are labeled as '1' and normal traffic as '0.'

Classification: Use the trained model to predict the probability of an incoming data point being an anomaly. Set a threshold to classify data points as normal or anomalous.

Decision Trees:

Overview: Decision Trees are a popular algorithm for classification and regression tasks. They partition the data into subsets based on features and make decisions based on a tree structure.

Application for Anomaly Detection:

Feature Selection: Identify and select relevant features for network traffic analysis.

Model Training: Train a decision tree model using labeled data, where anomalies are labeled as a separate class.

Classification: Use the decision tree to classify incoming data points. Anomalies will be identified if they fall into a distinct branch of the tree.

1. Set Up Snort:

Install and configure Snort: Begin by installing Snort on a dedicated server or sensor. Make sure Snort is configured to capture and analyze network traffic.

2. Define Your Network Baseline:

Establish a baseline for normal network behavior: This includes understanding typical traffic patterns, network protocols, and expected usage. Collect data over a reasonable time period to build an accurate baseline.

3. Create Custom Rules:

Develop custom Snort rules: Create rules specifically designed for anomaly detection. These rules should identify deviations from the established baseline.

Define anomaly thresholds: Set appropriate thresholds for specific network metrics, such as the number of connections per second, unusual data transfer rates, or the frequency of specific events. These thresholds will trigger alerts when exceeded.

4. Analyze Network Traffic:

Monitor network traffic: Allow Snort to passively inspect network traffic and compare it to the established baseline and custom rules.

Log anomalous events: Configure Snort to log events that match the custom anomaly detection rules. These logs will be used for further analysis.

5. Fine-Tune Snort Rules:

Adjust rule parameters: Continuously fine-tune the custom Snort rules and their parameters. This includes modifying thresholds and expanding or narrowing the scope of rules to reduce false positives and capture genuine anomalies.

6. Correlate Alerts:

Implement alert correlation: To differentiate between isolated false positives and true anomalies, use tools like Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) systems to correlate Snort alerts with other network events and data sources.

7. Continuous Monitoring:

Continuously monitor network traffic: Maintain ongoing monitoring and alerting. Anomalies can evolve, and the network baseline may change over time.

Periodically review and update custom rules and machine learning models to adapt to changing network conditions and emerging threats.

8. Incident Response:

Develop an incident response plan: Define a procedure for responding to detected anomalies. Outline how to investigate, mitigate, and document security incidents.

VII. RESULTS

Machine learning approach for anomaly detection

Fig:Test results

Fig:Anomaly Traffic Detection

Fig:F1 Score

Anomaly detection using snort:

Correlate Alerts:

```
# additions here.
alert icmp $EXTERNAL_NET any -> $HOME_NET any (msg:"its me"; sid:5889; rev:1;)
alert tcp any any -> $HOME_NET 21 (msg:"Ftp Attempted"; sid:60001; rev:1;)
alert tcp any any -> $HOME_NET 22 (msg:"SSH Attempted"; sid:60002; rev:1;)
```

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